

Refraction as an Example of a Photonic Bohm Aharonov Effect?

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In Newtonian mechanics a force changes momentum, for example it may change its magnitude only or its direction only or both. In the case of the Bohm Aharonov effect for a particle with rest mass there exists a potential which does not change momentum, but introduces a phase shift. Thus $\exp(ipx)$ for say an electron becomes $\exp(ip(x-x_0))$. Given that the form $\exp(-iEt+px)$ holds for both particles with rest mass and photons one might expect to find a Bohm Aharonov effect for photons. In (1), it is stated that a photonic Bohm Aharonov effect may be “induced by a dynamic modulation of a material’s permittivity”.

In this note we argue that the refraction of light seems to have the same form as a Bohm Aharonov effect in the sense that if one begins and ends in the same medium, the particle has the same energy E , momentum p , speed of light c and makes the same angle with the normal. In a Newtonian sense there has been no change to momentum, but the ray is shifted in the x direction from one that does not refract. It seems that this may be described by $\exp(ip_y y) \exp(ip_x(x-x_0))$ i.e. a phase shifted form suggesting that for the x direction one has a Bohm Aharonov effect.

We try to link this phase shift in the x direction to more general ideas. We argue as in (2) that a lack of information related to speed (i.e. the index of refraction) in the x direction leads to a conservation law related to speed in the x direction. This speed, however, is a hypothetical one such that it acts as a hypotenuse with $c/n(i)$ being a projection. This differs from the actual x component of velocity which is a projection of $c/n(i)$. Thus this actual x speed is not conserved meaning that light moving in a new medium will struck the outer bound at a different x than it would have it had not moved in a new medium. Thus the beam coming out of the new medium has the same E and p vector, but a shifted x i.e. there is a phase shift of the Bohm Aharonov type we argue even though we do not formally deal with a potential.

Particle with Rest Mass

Newton described particles with rest mass as undergoing changes in momentum (a vector) when acted on by a force which for conservative cases may be written as $F = -dV/dx$ where $V(x)$ is a potential. It is possible to change momentum without doing work i.e. changing energy as in the case of a particle moving in circular motion. One could consider one particle moving horizontally and another identical particle which gets caught in a circular force and is then released again when it is moving horizontally in the same direction. In such a case the particles would be at different positions even though they have the same energy and momentum. This would appear similar to a Bohm Aharonov situation which is sometimes described by a delay in time, but involves external manipulation i.e. releasing the particle from the circular force. Similarly one may decelerate and accelerate one particle back to its initial state, but this again involves external manipulation as well as energy and force input. The point we wish to make is that one may create Bohm Aharonov type shifts by introducing manipulation. In particular, in a quantum or photonic setting one could create particles/photons and different x points and they

would be shifted. This phase shift could not be distinguished from the Bohm Aharonov one as a phase shift is a phase shift.

For the case of an electron it is possible to have a magnetic potential which leads to a magnetic field which does not create any force on the electron. Nevertheless the electron moving through this magnetic potential acquires a phase. In other words even though there is no Newtonian interaction and no external manipulation a phase results. A phase shift in one direction, however, has the appearance of a particle starting from a different initial position i.e.

$$\exp(ipx - i \text{ phase}) = \exp(i p (x - x_0)) \quad \text{where } x_0 = \text{phase}/p \quad ((1))$$

If one performs an interference experiment at a screen of two electrons, one of which passed through a magnetic potential and the other which did not, they interfere, but one does not know whether there was one magnetic potential region or several or even no magnetic potential region and the particles were created at different positions. Thus a particular phase shift without any change in momentum or energy or external manipulation may be due to various causes. Nevertheless when the Bohm Aharonov effect was first experimentally demonstrated it was surprising because it meant that a particle with rest mass could be sensitive even to a potential which did not create a force.

Photon

The free particle action (relativistic and nonrelativistic although in the former E and p are defined differently) is $-Et+px$, but this is exactly the same Lorentz invariant form which appears in the argument $\cos(-Et+px)$ for the electric and magnetic fields of a photon. Furthermore photons have E and p just like a particle with rest mass and frequency is proportional to $1/E$ and wavelength to $1/p$ just as for a free particle with rest mass. This we argue follows from $-Et+px$. As a result, one might expect that a Bohm Aharonov effect might exist for a photon i.e. it may begin with an energy and momentum making a certain angle with the normal (say y direction) in a medium with an index of refraction of $n=1$ (pass through a region of space with a presence (i.e. different media instead of a magnetic potential) and return to a region with index of refraction of 1.

In such a case, the photon has the same energy, momentum, speed and makes the same angle with the y direction as it initially had. The only difference is that it is shifted in x (and time) from a photon that did not pass through the medium. If one considers a steady stream of photons along a certain angle then one does not need to worry about the shift in time. The shift in x , however, still remains so one has the form:

$\exp(i p_y y) \exp(i p_x x)$ for a photon stream which does not pass through various media with different indices of refraction and:

$\exp(i p_y y) \exp(i p_x (x-x_0))$ for a particle which passes through the medium

If one only considers the x direction, then it is as if one has two photons which were created at different points i.e. (x,y) and (x-x₀,y). These are out of phase and interfere. Thus it seems that a simple refraction scenario produces the same result as the Bohm Aharonov situation.

Does Refraction of Light Suggest that a Bohm Aharonov Effect Should Exist for Particles with Rest Mass?

Quantum mechanics treats free particles with rest mass as having a wavelength and frequency and undergoing diffraction and two slit interference just like light. Thus a particle-wave duality exists for these particles, but also for light as it imparts momentum like a particle. Historically even though particles with rest mass may have quantum properties, through the correspondence principle they are supposed to behave classically in a large energy level limit. Thus V(x) a potential which is a classical object is thought of in a classical manner as imparting impulses i.e. force. Refraction on the other hand is applied to light. Quantum mechanics, however, treats light and particles in a similar manner in terms of wave properties. Thus if light may pass through a medium which does not ultimately change its E and p vector, but produces a phase shift, one should expect a similar phenomenon may exist for a particle with rest mass. Otherwise there would be a way to distinguish between two types of E,p one which may be phase shifted with E and the p vector remaining unchanged and one which cannot. (In other words this feature, it seems, should have nothing to do with rest mass.)

Why a Shift in X?

It may be noted that in a refraction situation information is given about the y direction i.e. one has an initial and final y points for each index of refraction. "X" does not appear in this defining information. We argued in (2) that such an invariance of x in the problem leads to a conservation law in the x direction of hypothetical velocity H such that:

$$H \sin(A) = c/n_1 \quad \text{and} \quad H \sin(B) = c/n_2 \quad ((2))$$

Here the hypothetical velocity acts as a hypotenuse in the x direction and actual light speed is considered a projection of 90-A and 90-B where A and B are the angles of incidence and refraction measured with respect to the y-axis. Thus $n_1 \sin(A) = n_2 \sin(B)$ (Snell's law). Multiplying by p(vacuum) yields conservation of momentum along the x axis. H, however, is a hypothetical velocity, it is not the actual speed at which light traverses the x axis. That value is given by

$$\sin(A) c/n_1 \quad \text{and} \quad \sin(B) c/n_2. \quad ((3))$$

If one considers ((2)) and ((3)) then the x distance traveled in n₁ and n₂ differ for the same time interval t i.e.

$$t \sin(A) c/n_1 \quad \text{versus} \quad t \sin(B) c/n_2 \quad \text{or} \quad n_1 \sin(A) c / (n_1 n_1) \quad \text{versus} \quad n_1 \sin(A) c / (n_2 n_2)$$

Thus the conservation of hypothetical velocity which is a conservation law for a velocity along the x axis which is not the physical x velocity ensures that distance traveled along x for the same time intervals is different. This means that an incident ray which does not pass through a medium and an identical incident ray hit different x points after a time t. The y points are different as well, but for $n_1 < n_2$, but a diagram shows that even for the same y point the x values are different. Also the two beams are shifted in time.

For a steady beam of photons, however, one may forget about the shift in time, but the shift in x still exists. It suggests that the beam of photons passed through space which did not alter their energy or momentum or angle with the normal, but changed their x position as if they were created at a different point in space from the beam which did not undergo refraction i.e. the same y, but a different x point.

From the point of view of the x direction only there exists a phase shift between the refracted beam and a beam which does not refract. We argue that this is of the same physical form of the Bohm Aharonov effect even though we do not introduce a magnetic potential and consider its mathematical properties.

Thus a lack of information related to speed (i.e. the index of refraction) in a certain direction namely x leads to a conservation law of a hypothetical speed (not physical) speed) in the x direction. Because this is not the physical speed in the x direction which is conserved this leads to shifts in "x" for the same time interval which in turn lead to a phase shift in x.

Conclusion

We suggest two conclusions. First the refraction of a photon beam (with the medium surface lying in the x direction) yields a Bohm Aharonov effect in the x direction. Secondly in (2) we suggested that a lack of information related to the speed of light, namely the index of refraction, in the x direction lead to a conservation of a hypothetical velocity in the x direction such that this velocity acts as a hypotenuse with c/n_1 and c/n_2 being projections. (We also noted that this idea applies to reflection from a moving mirror using $v(\text{relative})$ instead to $c/n(i)$). For the physical velocity in the x direction c/n_1 and c/n_2 act as hypotenuses. Thus for the same time interval a conserved hypothetical x velocity means a nonconserved actual x velocity and different x points for the incident and refracted beams. Thus a beam refracting in a medium and returning into the same initial medium will have a shifted x. From the point of view of the x axis it is as if the light were created at a different x point, but with the same E,p and angle with the y axis as a nonrefracted beam. This, however, is identical to a phase shift, namely a Bohm Aharonov type phase shift.

References

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